

Privacy of Library Records

HUSSIN DAQAL

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Introduction

The library is a distinct preserve of the broadest ever range of ideas. Therefore, it is critical to safeguard the privacy of its records to guarantee all library users that they have the freedom to acquire knowledge from whichever library resource available to them without concerns of intimidation for the library resources they choose to use in the learning process (Oltmann,2017). Without the implementation of stringent data privacy measures, some scholars will be put off by the idea of others discovering their learning resources, and this might prevent the library from establishing a relationship that could lead to enlightenment and increase in knowledge in various fields (Rouse, 2020). According to the American Library Association code of ethics, privacy is guaranteed for public library users for information they seek, receive of the resources they borrow, referenced, received or disseminated ("Privacy: An Interpretation of the Library Bill of Rights", 2006). The right to privacy is provided to all library users irrespective of their backgrounds, race or any other binaries used to discriminate people.

Library and information science professionals revere individual privacy, as well as the safeguarding of private data pooled between individual library users and institutions. The library and its users establish a relationship centered on confidentiality and professionals in this field will adopt suitable approaches to make sure that user data is protected from usages that were not initially planned for (Caldwell-Stone and Robinson, 2017). The advancement of technology has ensured that library services delivery has evolved and users no longer need to access the library physically. Today, users can use the internet of things (IoT) to access library resources. While advanced technology is welcomed, it also creates various means of violating personal privacy (Caldwell-Stone and Robinson, 2017). It is for this reason that this paper studies the various

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binaries of privacy of library records. It is a policy that will help conceptualize a framework where data privacy of library records is ensured while ethical and technological issues are addressed.

Problem Statement and Research Objectives

Privacy is vital to create room for free speech, deliberation, and correlation. As such, library users require data privacy for their library records to facilitate the freedom of inquiry (Blanchard, 2016). In a library, users are concerned about issues such as unnecessary and sometimes uncomfortable scrutiny of their inquiries, library searches, resources chosen among other activities a user can participate in the library. Confidentiality is essential in this case. Confidentiality happens when libraries acquire personal identifying information of its users and protect the information from unauthorized access (Johnson, 2018). The objective of the paper is to examine how the issue of privacy for library records affects library and information science professionals today. To achieve this objective, the paper will try and answer the following research questions:

- How does data privacy of library records impact library and information science professionals today?
- What are the trends and challenges confronting data privacy measures of library records?
- Which processes and technologies facilitate data privacy of library records?
- What re the ethics, values, and foundation of data privacy for library records?

Literature Review

Libraries have played a critical role in shaping world history since they were first established (Tait, Martzoukou, and Reid, 2016). The data privacy issues discussed today mirror

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the ones that concern library privacy. For instance, the issues include the exploration of the conflict of interests as well as the conflict between realism and perception; how technology can be applied to improve or reduce data privacy, how library users have different interest based on things such as age groups as well as issues that are associated with broad binaries, for example, national security and the use of library records commercially (Kim and Noh, 2014). Libraries have played a leading role in debates on the application of technology to increase access to library resources. All libraries, including virtual and physical libraries' core mission, are to organize library resources so that library users can access the information they need. It is no surprise; therefore, that library and information science specialists have been among the biggest discussers of data privacy issues (“The National Academies Press”, 2007).

The library foundations and values are centered on coalescing concrete access to information with the idea that library persons would take advantage of the opportunity and acquire knowledge and this was a vital driver of the establishment of public libraries and influenced the librarian and information scientist professions (Walters, 2014). Instead of viewing themselves as information concierges, professionals in the field viewed their role as that of teachers and enablers of knowledge acquisition. As such, the professionals redefined their roles from that of storing the information in libraries to that of spreading the information to the library patrons. The professionals could only distribute information library patrons want to access and not the information the professionals deemed appropriate. The professionals could help the patrons in the selection process, but the final decision on which library resources to borrow, read or cite was left to the patrons (Lambert, Parker and Bashir, 2016). Critically, library and information science professionals had the critical task of implementing technologies and processes that facilitate information access for library patrons.

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Library records require proper management to ensure suiting the organization of information and protection of people's data privacy. The process of managing library encompasses the entire library life cycle, starting at the creation of resources and including other steps such as retrieval and dissemination of information. A good management system minimizes risks such as the risks associated with data privacy reach (Wang, 2015). While libraries are different in terms of how they operate, the best management system depends on the systems used by a specific library. Since a library avails a full spectrum of information and knowledge to library patrons, there is a need for a proper approach of organizing and keeping the library resources to ensure privacy. Some of the processes involved include cataloging and classification (Eze, 2012). The two processes are essential even with advanced technology as they remain the main techniques professionals in the field can organize library records for easy access by patrons. Library technologies allow the transmission, storage, creation, and dissemination of information using various technological devices (Vijayakumar and Vijayan, 2011).

Ethical Considerations

The process of gathering and synthesizing data has been enhanced by advanced technology and the big data collected today can expand people's understanding of how user needs and behaviors evolve and hence provide an opportunity to improve service delivery (Sivarajah et al., 2017). Libraries are aware of their vital role in society. They are, individually and collectively, involved in the discussion on the way libraries can be ethical in their involvement in educational analytics processes, and what qualifies as proper ethical conducts when it comes to the use of private data gathered from library patrons. Consequently, library and information science experts are consciously aware of the results of violating the professional ethics codes. The ALA code comprises several elements (Asher et al., 2018). The most

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prominent among them relate to concerns such as upholding the principles of intellectual autonomy and fighting back all attempts to gag access to library resources. Other critical ethical concerns touch on how to safeguard library patrons' right to privacy and confidentiality so that the information referenced, disseminated or used is not used to intimidate them. All the professionals in the field respect each other, collaborate to ensure working conditions are better and guarantee fairness and good faith when it comes to protecting user privacy (Hoq, 2012).

Trends and Challenges

The current trend in library resources management involves the integration of information technology to provide users with digital libraries that can be accessed remotely. While there are many advantages such as ease of access, reduced time wastage and proper utilization of resources, several challenges arise. Most of the challenges are concerned with security and data privacy (Breeding, 2011). The issues that need to be tackled include protecting the information infrastructure; identifying and authenticating security and user's data privacy; values and guidelines; access and management of digital library records, ethics of privacy and the processes of implementing and assessing digital library records (Al-Suqri, 2009). Since technology is continually evolving and becoming more sophisticated each passing day, there is a need to develop or revise the existing guidelines from time to time to address the unique challenges of adopting new methods of accessing library resources (Jones, n.d.). As a consequence, library and information science professional roles will include securing data privacy for library patrons, so that information such as data logs and records are not accessed by an unauthorized person(s).

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Conclusion

Data privacy of library records is an increasingly important subject for library and information science professionals. Traditionally, these professionals work involved securing information in libraries so that users can access it. With advanced technology, the roles were refined, and professionals in the field are now educators as well as enablers of library resource access. The paper has successfully demonstrated that data privacy is an important subject in the field. It is facilitated through processes and technologies. The current global trends indicate that digital libraries will be a central element of future library operations. However, challenges as regards security and privacy persist. A framework of addressing these issues involves developing and refining existing policies to ensure data privacy, and hence library users can have the freedom to gain knowledge. On the whole, data privacy for library records is a big issue of concern for library patrons and professionals in the field recognize this and are actively involved in discussions to develop appropriate intervention measures.

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